

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Pervasive and Mobile Computing

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/pmc

A customizable benchmarking tool for evaluating personalized thermal comfort provisioning in smart spaces using Digital Twins

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Individual thermal comfort
 Benchmarking
 Energy consumption
 Digital twin

ABSTRACT

Providing proper thermal comfort to individual occupants is crucial to improve well-being and work efficiency. However, Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems are responsible for a large portion of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in buildings. To combat the current energy crisis and climate change, innovative ways have been proposed to leverage pervasive and mobile computing systems equipped with sensors and smart devices for occupant thermal comfort satisfaction and efficient HVAC management. However, evaluating these thermal comfort provision solutions presents considerable difficulties. Conducting experiments in the real world poses challenges such as privacy concerns and the high costs of installing and maintaining sensor infrastructure. On the other hand, experiments with simulations need to accurately model real-world conditions and ensure the reliability of the simulated data.

To address these challenges, we present Co-zyBench, an innovative benchmarking tool that leverages Digital Twin (DT) technology to assess personalized thermal comfort provision systems. Our benchmark employs a simulation-based DT for the building and its HVAC system, another DT for simulating the dynamic behavior of its occupants, and a co-simulation middleware to achieve a seamless connection of the DTs. Our benchmark includes mechanisms to generate DTs based on data such as architectural models of buildings, sensor readings, and occupant thermal sensation data. It also includes reference DTs based on standard buildings, HVAC configurations, and various occupant thermal profiles. As a result of the evaluation, the benchmark generates a report based on expected energy consumption, carbon emission, thermal comfort, and occupant equity metrics. We present the evaluation results of state-of-the-art thermal comfort provisioning systems within a DT based on a real building and several reference DTs.

1. Introduction

Efficient energy management in buildings has become a pressing concern as Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems contribute nearly half of the total energy consumption in commercial buildings [1]. Predictions indicate that global cooling demand will triple by 2050 due to climate change and urban expansion [2]. Additionally, given the global challenges posed by climate change, efforts are increasingly focused on reducing carbon emissions rather than merely cutting energy consumption [3]. Some countries have set targets to achieve net zero emissions [4], making the development of green and low-carbon buildings

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmcj.2025.102076>

Received 2 August 2024; Received in revised form 28 April 2025; Accepted 19 May 2025

Available online 4 June 2025

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and corresponding technologies essential for achieving carbon neutrality. While energy conservation and environmental protection are crucial, it is equally imperative to prioritize the assurance of people's thermal comfort. People spend most of their time inside buildings and various studies have revealed the direct associations between indoor thermal environment and occupants' cognitive functions and productivity [5,6]. The intrinsic challenge in providing thermal comfort is that thermal sensations vary among individuals and have been identified as a factor of several drivers [7] including physiological (such as age, sex and fitness); psychological (including effects of personal control, thermo-specific self-efficacy and personality); and contextual factors of the built environment [8–10].

The growing emphasis on occupant comfort and energy efficiency has highlighted the need for advanced thermal comfort provision systems that can simultaneously enhance thermal comfort and improve energy efficiency by regulating the indoor environment. Pervasive and mobile computing technologies are essential to design such thermal comfort provision systems. In particular, wearable devices, including wrist-worn temperature sensors or infrared cameras, have been explored to monitor changes in human body temperature to estimate individuals' thermal comfort [11–14]. In addition, mobile devices, such as smartphones or smartwatches, have been proposed as a mechanism for the occupants of a building to report their thermal sensation [15,16]. Also, the Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning techniques, such as Reinforcement Learning (RL), have been leveraged to optimize HVAC control [17,18].

Several challenges hinder the development and evaluation of such thermal comfort provision systems: (1) Real-world experiments are often time-consuming and costly, involving the installation and maintenance of devices and the recruitment of participants. (2) The collection of data from real buildings and occupants for experimentation is limited due to privacy and operational concerns. (3) Comparing the performance of different systems requires a consistent experiment context to reduce the influence of external factors which is nearly impossible in real-world experiments. (4) The inability to evaluate systems across diverse scenarios can result in skewed or incomplete conclusions or bias, as system performance may vary significantly under different conditions. For example, previous evaluations have focused primarily on buildings in the US, Europe, and China [11], which may not adequately capture system performance under the unique climate demands of other regions.

To address these challenges, simulation-based evaluations offer a promising alternative [19]. Realistic simulations of buildings and occupants allow controlled and repeatable experiments across various scenarios, achieving comprehensive evaluations without the logistical and ethical issues of real-world experiments. Additionally, simulations provide quick assessments, facilitating more efficient iterations which means developers can receive faster evaluation results, accelerating the development process. For these reasons, simulations of buildings and occupants have been extensively utilized to assess the performance of building management strategies [20]. In fact, their effectiveness in energy-related analyses has been widely validated [19,21]. However, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of these simulations is vital and challenging. The accuracy of these simulations heavily depends on the ability of the user to input precise parameters that effectively represent the actual properties of a building. Learning and modeling such sophisticated simulations often consume considerable time and effort. Additionally, taking into account occupant behavior in smart building management is considered beneficial to improve productivity, comfort, and energy savings [22]. However, it is often overlooked and is identified as a major factor contributing to the discrepancy between simulations and real building performance [23]. This underscores the imminent need for more efficient and user-friendly methods to build simulation models that accurately incorporate occupant behaviors into building simulations.

Therefore, we propose a novel benchmarking platform, Co-zyBench [24], to address these challenges. The benchmark is designed to evaluate and optimize thermal comfort provision systems by allowing for consistent evaluation, enabling researchers to refine their systems through comparative analysis. Co-zyBench incorporates data grounded in real-world references (see Section 5), such as actual historical weather records and building material properties defined based on industry standards, assisting developers in easily composing experiment scenarios based on their requirements. Co-zyBench utilizes Digital Twins (DTs) which are virtual representations of physical entities to simulate the performance of HVAC systems in buildings and the dynamic behavior of occupants including their movement and thermal sensations. DTs for building and occupants interact to realistically simulate the impact of occupant behavior on building performance. Integrating DTs into the benchmarking process offers multiple advantages. Firstly, it is a cost-effective alternative to real-world building evaluations, enabling users to consider a diverse range of environments that may not be feasible in physical settings. Secondly, users such as building administrators who have their own building models can assess the potential performance of various systems in their scenarios without actual implementation.

Co-zyBench employs state-of-the-art simulation tools to model occupant movement and thermal sensations within these DTs, using historical occupant data, and to simulate indoor temperature changes and energy consumption caused by HVAC manipulation. A co-simulation middleware in Co-zyBench facilitates interaction between the DTs. This middleware moves occupants within the building, generating their current thermal sensation in response to the dynamic environmental conditions. The thermal comfort provision system being evaluated should take into account building and occupants status and control the HVAC systems accordingly. Additionally, the benchmark provides users with different types of reference scenarios of DTs and also optional ways to customize the evaluation scenarios based on their requirements, providing benchmark users the flexibility to evaluate their systems on various scenarios. Co-zyBench proposes five main metrics to evaluate the performance of thermal comfort provision systems with respect to their ability to: (1) Ensure general occupant comfort; (2) Aim to prevent consistent discomfort for a minority group; (3) Effectiveness in reducing energy consumption; (4) Environmental impact by CO₂ emission; and (5) Overall performance across the above metrics. In summary, key contributions of Co-zyBench include:

- It is the first benchmark to evaluate the impact of thermal comfort provision systems on individuals' comfort, comfort equality, energy consumption and environmental impact.

- It offers simulation-based Digital Twin models that reflect and predict occupant dynamic behavior and building energy performance.
- It includes an individual thermal sensation modeler designed to account for occupant movement in the building and diversity in thermal preference.
- It integrates a co-simulation strategy that mediates between DTs of occupants and buildings to provide a realistic and dynamically evolving context.
- It proposes optional methods to customize building and occupant DTs to help users create scenarios according to their specific requirements.

The key novelty of this paper, extending the initial contributions in [24], is the addition of different methods to provide benchmark users with more flexible configurations for comprehensive evaluation. In particular, Co-zyBench is enhanced to support both importing complex DTs from users defined in the standard NSGI-LD format and generating synthetic DTs with simple inputs such as the number of floors, rooms and occupants. We extend the semantic property graph by incorporating more details about the building and occupant to provide more realistic simulations. This includes adjustable construction elements (e.g., fenestration, materials) and environmental factors (e.g., outdoor temperature, humidity) for simulating the thermal performance of buildings, as well as customizable sensors for monitoring occupant behaviors. Additionally, we integrate extra reference scenarios involving buildings, occupants, HVAC systems, and environment settings. Reference thermal comfort provision systems are also provided for users and can be used as baselines to against which to evaluate. We also introduce two new metrics on environmental impact and overall performance to offer a broader evaluation scope. Finally, we conducted additional experiments using the new Digital Twin generation approaches and reference systems.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 overviews the state of the art. Section 3 presents a motivating scenario and the overall methodology of the benchmark by the framework design and utilization process. Section 4 details the design of each component of the benchmark. Section 5 explains the other components of the benchmark including evaluation metrics, reference scenarios, and thermal comfort provision systems. Section 6 shows scenario implementations in the benchmark and some evaluation analyses based on the evaluation. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. Related work

The proliferation of pervasive computing technologies like smartphones and sensors has spurred significant research into personalized thermal comfort in buildings [11,14,25]. These works primarily address the challenge of estimating or capturing occupants' thermal sensations and preferences, employing two main approaches. Given that most occupants likely possess a personal device like a smartphone, several methods involve soliciting direct input from users. This includes collecting demographic data (age, height, weight, gender) to infer thermal sensation [26] or directly asking them to report their current thermal comfort [15,27]. These data can be also combined to develop more robust personalized thermal comfort models [27]. The main applicability challenge of this approach is motivating consistent participation from occupants and managing incomplete data. A different approach is to leverage interconnected networks of sensors, actuators, and devices to continuously collect and transmit data on energy usage, environmental conditions, and occupant behavior [11,14]. Various devices, including wearables [11] and infrared cameras [14], have been used to monitor temperature changes and predict thermal preferences. Additional data like heartbeat rates [25], obtained via mobile devices [28] and in-ear microphones [29], or physical activity levels, detected through wearables [30,31], also contribute to understanding occupants' thermal sensations. The main applicability challenges for sensor-based systems are the costs associated with widespread deployment and encouraging users to share data from personal devices.

Another research topic that has received significant attention is the efficient control and management of HVAC systems to meet the balance of energy conservation and thermal comfort requirements (since HVAC systems account for the largest portion of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions in buildings [32]). A popular approach to reduce HVAC energy consumption is to deactivate the HVAC system in unoccupied rooms through occupancy sensing [33,34]. Additional strategies involve optimizing HVAC control by estimating potential thermal comfort levels. For example, Barone et al. [35] proposed a thermal comfort model based on physiological parameters that can achieve precise prediction of thermal comfort. This model is used to evaluate potential HVAC control actions, optimizing the system to enhance thermal comfort. Liu et al. [36] utilized reinforcement learning algorithms for occupant-centric HVAC and window control to enhance HVAC energy efficiency. Previous work on energy conservation, in general, focuses on maintaining the general thermal comfort of people, often overlooking the diversity of individual thermal preferences. This is largely due to the challenges associated with evaluating such systems, making it difficult to propose solutions that account for varied thermal preferences.

Mims et al. [37] demonstrate a causal relationship between building energy performance benchmarking and energy savings, reporting a reduction of 3% to 8% in gross energy consumption. Consequently, benchmarking for building energy performance has undergone extensive research and continuous improvements. The prevalent method in the literature for assessing building energy performance involves using datasets obtained through monitoring or questionnaires [38]. While some studies benchmark their systems in actual buildings [39], these approaches are often labor-intensive, costly, and sometimes impractical. In response to these challenges, simulation-based and DT-based approaches have gained popularity in recent years for their ability to deliver cost-effective, scalable, and reproducible benchmarking solutions [40,41]. However, these benchmarking efforts have primarily focused on building energy performance and have neglected the occupants' comfort, particularly diverse individual thermal comfort. Considering the strong link between energy performance and comfort, evaluating both factors together has become increasingly essential and is now integral to thermal comfort provision systems.

Using Digital Twin (DT) models for thermal comfort provision systems is a promising avenue for the design, optimization, and maintenance of HVAC systems [42–44]. Co-zyBench leverages this approach by facilitating the benchmarking of such systems within a DT environment. For instance, Khayatian et al. [40] used DTs to analyze the energy consumption of various HVAC control systems, providing a platform for comparative assessments in identical environmental conditions. They also measured thermal comfort by tracking deviations from the recommended indoor temperature range. However, current methodologies often overlook the subjective nature of comfort and the diversity of human profiles [45]. Very few studies have considered performance across different regions and climate zones [38,45], which may significantly influence overall energy consumption [46]. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has fully integrated simulations that encompass both synthetic yet realistic buildings and occupants, including simulating occupant interactions with their environment and the consequent thermal sensations. Crucially, these simulations should reflect the diversity of occupants and climate regions, an aspect that remains underrepresented in current evaluation methods. Co-zyBench aims to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive and realistic benchmarking platform.

3. Overview of Co-zyBench

3.1. Motivating scenario

Imagine a multinational corporation with office buildings throughout the globe. Take one of the offices as an example where employees move between shared spaces such as office rooms and meeting areas (e.g., the office building in Fig. 7(a)). Each of the occupants has unique thermal comfort preferences: some might prefer a colder environment, others warmer. Based on those preferences and environmental conditions, users will have different thermal comfort sensations at different points in time. Note that sensations are highly dynamic and might depend on the activity being performed or the space where they are located. Consider the building equipped with an HVAC system that regulates the room temperature. The corporation is exploring the installation of thermal comfort provision systems in each office building to balance occupant thermal comfort and energy efficiency. For instance, these systems could collect or estimate the thermal sensations of the employees and adjust room temperature accordingly. Achieving both thermal comfort and energy efficiency simultaneously is always challenging, as these factors present a trade-off against one another (e.g., in summer the system might need to consume more energy to keep people cool). This trade-off might be different depending on the diversity of the workforce in each specific office and/or the climate zone/region where the building is located. Also, different thermal comfort provision systems might deal with the trade-off differently. For instance, they might decide to prioritize decreasing energy consumption or increasing thermal comfort for the majority of employees (disregarding the preferences of minorities). Hence, before making a decision, the corporation would like to explore the performance of the different systems to decide which best fits their requirements.

Ideally, one would evaluate the performance of various candidate thermal comfort provision systems in each of the office buildings. However, evaluating the systems in real buildings is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and impractical. For example, a proper evaluation might require deploying new sensors and collecting data for weeks at different times of the year (e.g., summer vs. winter). It might also result in impacting the productivity of employees while the evaluation is taking place since the system might make unexpected changes to the temperature levels. Co-zyBench makes this process easier as we describe next.

3.2. Architecture of Co-zyBench

The goal of Co-zyBench is to provide a simulation-based testing platform specifically designed to evaluate thermal comfort provision systems that leverage sensors and smart devices for HVAC control. A typical thermal comfort provision system comprises three key components: (1) Sensation Collector collects data related to occupant thermal comfort, in particular, individual sensation data including subjective feedback from occupants and/or objective data from sensors. (2) Sensation Aggregator aggregates the individual thermal sensations into a collective measure of comfort for a group of occupants. (3) HVAC Controller translates the aggregated thermal comfort data into actionable HVAC control commands. Co-zyBench connects to a thermal comfort provision system and runs a set of benchmarking experiments to assess its performance in different situations. Co-zyBench is an open-source platform and the code is available on GitHub [47]. The benchmark includes three primary components (see Fig. 1):

- **Occupant Digital Twin** which creates a virtual representation of building occupants, incorporating both static and dynamic attributes, and maintains it updated during the benchmarking of the thermal comfort provision system (see more details in Section 4.2). Static attributes include profiles related to thermal sensation, such as age, gender, activity level and heart rate. The most important dynamic attribute handled by the occupant DT is the location of the occupants. To this end, it uses a trajectory simulator to generate realistic trajectories of occupants in the space based on events occurring in it (e.g., meetings or lunch breaks in the office space of our motivating scenario). These attributes, along with dynamic data from the smart building DT such as the current environmental conditions in each room (e.g., temperature), are used by the Sensation Modeler component to model how occupants would feel (e.g., warm or slightly cold). This classification is achieved using a machine learning algorithm trained on a historical dataset containing past thermal sensation records. On the other hand, the attributes are also used by the Sensation Collector module of the thermal comfort provision system to estimate how the occupants might be feeling in a given environment at a given time (see Section 5.2.1). In other words, the Sensation Collector is used to predict thermal sensations that are simulated by the Sensation Modeler.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Co-zyBench benchmark.

- **Smart Building Digital Twin** which maintains a DT of the building including its HVAC system. It is responsible for controlling the digital representation of the HVAC system and simulating temperature variations in different spaces. These simulations consider both static building models (e.g., the floorplan) as well as dynamic environmental factors (such as occupant location and activities) which are obtained from the occupant DT. Co-zyBench's primary focus is on benchmarking the impact of the thermal comfort provision system on comfort and energy. So, the smart building DT does not handle digital representations of other energy systems in the building (e.g., lighting control). These could potentially be integrated using our co-simulation middleware but that is out of the scope of our current work.
- **Co-simulation Middleware** which serves as the communication bridge between the two DTs and the thermal comfort provision system to be benchmarked. The main task is to exchange information through the synchronization module about the indoor thermal conditions from the smart building DT with the occupant DT to generate realistic changes in occupants' thermal sensations. Then, the Building Management System, which is controlled by the thermal comfort provision system, generates control actions for the HVAC system based on the occupant sensations. During co-simulation, the middleware interacts with the Results Collector module to collect evaluation metrics that are pre-defined in Co-zyBench.

For users to evaluate their thermal comfort provision systems using Co-zyBench, they need to integrate their systems into the platform. To facilitate the evaluation of the systems in Co-zyBench, a wrapper encapsulates the Sensation Collector, Sensation Aggregator, and HVAC Controller into a cohesive thermal comfort provision system. This wrapper communicates information from the co-simulator (e.g., the thermal sensation of users, state of the HVAC system, etc.) to the system and from the system (e.g., the specific temperature setpoint for the general HVAC system or each room) to the co-simulator. Co-zyBench includes a set of reference thermal comfort provision systems as well as a library of Reference Scenarios (see Section 5.3.1) including DT configurations for buildings and occupants. This is particularly helpful as it allows users to focus on implementing only the aspects of the evaluation they are interested in, rather than developing the entire setup from scratch. For example, building administrators testing the energy performance of their buildings can leverage the reference occupant DTs and thermal comfort provision systems. To provide a comprehensive evaluation of the systems, Co-zyBench includes a set of metrics that assess performance in terms of energy efficiency, thermal comfort, equitable thermal comfort provision, environmental impact, and overall performance (see Section 5.1).

3.3. How to use Co-zyBench

Co-zyBench is structured to be a highly adaptable and user-friendly platform, enabling the evaluation of various thermal comfort provision systems within DTs that reflect the user's actual buildings or a range of pre-included templates.

Fig. 2 depicts the overall steps required to set up Co-zyBench and use it to evaluate a thermal comfort provision system using DTs based on standard scenarios or a real building the end-user might have access to. First, the end-user begins by importing the thermal comfort provision system they wish to evaluate into Co-zyBench (**Step 1**). Co-zyBench includes several baseline systems for end-users to compare with or to use as a reference. Details about the proposed baseline systems are introduced in Section 5.2. Then, the user selects an evaluation scenario which can be either: a customized DT based on a specific building and occupant characteristics (**Step 2.a**); or one of the Co-zyBench reference DTs which are standard scenarios Co-zyBench provides (**Step 2.b**) (see Section 4). For the former, Co-zyBench offers tools that simplify the modeling of DTs by converting building and occupant data models into the proper format for Co-zyBench co-simulation. For the latter, Co-zyBench includes built-in DTs representing common scenarios such as offices, hospitals, and hotels. Finally, the user runs the benchmark (**Step 3**) and obtains the evaluation results (see Section 5.1). A more detailed guideline with examples is provided in the Co-zyBench Github repository [47]. In our running example, the corporation should develop an actual thermal comfort provision system and import it to Co-zyBench. For this purpose, the evaluation scenario can be customized with specific data models such as building data models (see Section 4.1). Co-zyBench can be used to complete missing data and generate building simulation models. At the same time, the corporation must define the occupant profiles and the events that occupants attend in order to simulate the trajectories and thermal sensations of occupants. Once these configurations are complete, simulations can be executed in order to compare simulation results and select the most suitable thermal comfort provision system for their buildings.

Fig. 2. Co-zyBench workflow.

4. Co-zyBench core components

4.1. Smart building digital twin

Providing benchmark users with diverse buildings and HVAC models contributes to performing robustness testing of thermal comfort provision systems. However, exhaustively defining the diversity of building types worldwide is practically impossible due to its complexity [48]. To tackle this, the NGS-LD specification offers a standardized approach for creating DTs by providing a set of data models for smart environments [49] that we integrate and further extend in our work. NGS-LD builds on the JSON-LD format [50], a JSON-based serialization for Linked Data. Our NGS-LD building model is a Building Information Models (BIM)-based model combining semantics from BIM models with dynamic data and DT functionalities such as occupant behavior observations, HVAC actuation and environmental conditions. The model can be extracted through various data sources. For instance, in our experiments (see Section 6.1.2), we extract static data related to the building envelope from a real building's BIM static model. Subsequently, we utilize Co-zyBench's predefined reference building materials and HVAC system definitions to construct the building's structure and HVAC system. The dynamic information such as the real-time data is automatically generated during the co-simulation runtime, ensuring compatibility and interoperability within the semantic models. As depicted in Fig. 3, a building can be represented as a *property graph* which defines *entities* (e.g., Space), *relationships* (e.g., hasSpace), and *properties* (e.g., geoLocation) as the key components of the building information model serialized in NGS-LD. Using the building specification, Co-zyBench supports both the definition of a real building (spaces, devices, etc.), as well as existing buildings already defined in NGS-LD format.

To define the DT of a real smart building, the first step involves defining the smart building's NGS-LD property graph (Fig. 3) based on its building (floor plan, etc.) and deployed devices (HVAC system, IoT devices, etc.). The building includes properties about its location and environment. Location information, such as time zone, geographic coordinates, elevation, climate zone, etc., is required to accurately simulate the outdoor environment and climate conditions which refer to how well a building maintains a comfortable indoor temperature. Specifically, the time zone, geographic coordinates, and elevation help calculate the solar position and solar radiation intensity along with the weather conditions which are critical inputs for evaluating the thermal performance of the building's heat gain, envelope insulation, and HVAC system efficiency. The climate zone in which the building is located is represented based on the climate zone definition from the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) standard [51]. This climate zone classification is crucial for accurately modeling the building's thermal performance, including the selection of construction materials, and for designing HVAC systems with the appropriate capacity. In addition, a building has an *environment* which is used to simulate the climate condition and compute potential carbon emissions caused by the HVAC systems. To this end, the *environment* entity contains properties for the weather and carbon emissions throughout the whole year. We design this entity based on the EnergyPlus Weather File (EPW) format which has been adopted as a standard format by most building simulation tools [52]. Co-zyBench users need to specify various parameters about the weather including dry bulb temperature and dew point temperature in Celsius degree, atmospheric pressure in Pa, solar radiation in Wh/m², wind speed in m/s, etc. We calculate the carbon emissions of the building based on the carbon intensity which is defined in gCO₂eq/kWh, meaning how much gram of CO₂ equivalent would be emitted by consuming per kilowatt hour of electricity.

Moreover, the modeling of building construction materials is also required for users to define in case they need to simulate the thermal performance accurately. We begin by including the concept of *space*, which represents metadata about the various rooms and areas. Each *space* is characterized by its type, maximum capacity, a set of windows and doors, relative coordinates that shape the space, along with space envelope surfaces which include walls, floors, ceilings and openings that are defined using their dimensions, positions, and material properties. Each surface is composed of multiple materials, defined by their insulation properties, thermal mass, thickness, and other relevant factors, to determine heat transfer and heat storage properties. Each space has a set of constructions for the walls, floors, ceilings, and fenestration, all composed of multiple materials.

Both *Building* and *Space* have relationships with the entity *Thermal Zone*. A thermal zone is a collection of spaces that share the same thermostat and are controlled as a whole by the HVAC systems. Each thermal zone should be connected with at least one

Fig. 3. The smart building-based NGSI-LD property graph.

HVAC system. An HVAC system consists of multiple *HVAC objects* to indicate its internal structure, such as heating units, cooling units, fans, and outdoor air systems, as well as settings like connections, capacity, coefficient of performance, and airflow rate. HVAC is a type of *Device* which also includes other devices such as appliances, lighting, and IoT devices for environmental monitoring and occupancy detection. A *Device* is defined by its type, specifications including power consumption, fraction radiant for calculating heat release, and schedules that define activity patterns. *Device* and *HVAC* can have sensors and actuators to acquire observations and provide actuation for thermal comfort provision systems. For example, a head counter can be considered a virtual device with sensors in each zone to provide observations of occupant numbers.

As already pointed out, these building representations will be utilized for simulations as part of the Co-simulation middleware (Section 4.3). Note that acquiring such smart building data models can be time-consuming and it is out of the scope of this paper. Users can rely on building reports or sensor-driven pervasive computing systems to obtain this information [53] and import it into Co-zyBench. For example, LiDAR sensors and RGB-D cameras can achieve the automatic generation of building models [54,55].

4.2. Occupant digital twin

To create the occupant DT, Co-zyBench considers three main aspects: their profiles that influence occupant thermal comfort preferences, their real-time location, and their thermal sensation in a specific location with a specific temperature. We propose the NGSI-LD specification to support a standard way of defining building occupants. As depicted in Fig. 4, in the context of our running example, an *Occupant* (e.g., Jim) belongs to an *Occupant Group* (e.g., seller) that attend an *Event* (e.g., meeting with the boss) that belongs to an *Event Type* (e.g., weekly meeting). Events are located in *Space* where occupants can exploit *device* while roaming from one event to another. Specifically, occupants are grouped based on two factors: time profiles and event affinities. The time profile property comprises a list of time intervals indicating the duration occupants stay in the building. Each interval is defined by a start time, end time, and deviation to introduce randomness among individuals. Event affinity indicates the likelihood that an occupant group will attend specific events. For example, a manager must attend a meeting, but some employees may be absent. In addition, events are categorized based on their types. An event type is defined with a list of possible spaces where they can take place and an occupant affinity that is used to restrict the minimum and maximum number of occupants from each group to attend. Moreover, each *Space* is associated with the building model and specifies its capacity to limit the number of occupants it can hold. Both spaces and occupants can be equipped with *Devices* that are also associated with the building model. For instance, occupants may have sensors that record movement trajectories, while rooms might have sensors detecting occupant-related observations such as motion sensors. These observations are integrated as inputs to the thermal comfort provision systems, enabling more comprehensive control and management.

Fig. 4. The occupant-based NGSI-LD property graph.

Secondly, occupants are diverse with their thermal preferences (e.g., based on their gender [8], age [9], or activity [56]). Hence, to reflect this diversity, it is required to model the diverse characteristics present among individuals. This information will be abstracted and used to estimate their thermal preferences (e.g., whether they would prefer warmer or colder temperatures or whether they would be neutral). Thirdly, based on the thermal profiles there is a requirement to model how a person would feel based on the current temperature. To achieve this, we use the Thermal Sensation Vote (TSV) scale, which serves as the de facto standard for representing thermal comfort preferences in the literature. The TSV consists of seven categories with values from -3 to 3 : “cold”, “cool”, “slightly cool”, “neutral”, “slightly warm”, “warm”, and “hot”, based on [8], men feel comfortable when the temperature is $22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, this translates to 0 on the scale, while women would feel comfortable at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The profiles and activity schedules of the occupants enable the modeling of their moving trajectories which is essential for representing how the environmental conditions of a space will impact their thermal sensation. To this end, we integrate a trajectory generation model and a sensation estimation model along with the NGSI-LD property graph which defines the semantic representation of space, occupants and events. Their integration extracts meaningful patterns from sensorized spaces which are subsequently applied within an event-driven simulation to produce synthetic but realistic data, encompassing events, trajectories and thermal sensations. For example, the benchmark generates realistic trajectories of occupants attending a meeting in a meeting room within the smart building and estimates their thermal sensations based on their thermal preferences and the indoor environment.

Algorithm 1 Thermal Sensation Generation

Input: Occupants P , Events E , Spaces S , Simulation Time t , Building DT B , Sensation Collector SC

Output: Current Occupants Thermal Sensation TS

```

1:  $event, occupants = traj\_learning(P, E, S)$ 
2:  $traj = traj\_generation(event, occupants)$ 
3:  $TS \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4: for  $p$  in  $P$  do
5:    $loc\_p = locate(traj, p, t)$ 
6:   if ( $loc\_p$  in  $B.get\_space()$ ) then
7:      $current\_temp = B.get\_temp(t, loc\_p)$ 
8:      $ts\_p = SA(p, current\_temp)$ 
9:      $TS \leftarrow TS \cup tc\_p$ 
10:  end if
11: end for
12: return  $TS$ 

```

Algorithm 1 shows the high-level process followed by the benchmark to generate thermal sensations, which is the key process of the occupant DT. Initially, the occupants, events, and space configurations are provided as input to the *traj_learning* module which extracts features related to the simulated scenario and generates the occurrence of *events* interconnected with the *occupants* (line 1 in Alg. 1). Subsequently, trajectories are generated for each *occupant* based on the corresponding *event* following the process in [57]. These trajectories detail each person’s location within the building over a specific time period. Thus, at any time t , the location of occupant p can be determined from the generated trajectories (line 5). If the occupant is within the spaces of the building DT B , the system retrieves the current indoor temperature. With the indoor temperature and the occupants’ profiles, the Sensation Collector estimates the occupant’s thermal sensation. Eventually, the algorithm returns the predicted thermal sensations of all occupants.

4.3. Co-simulation middleware

The co-simulation middleware connects the two DTs (building and occupant) through a synchronization mechanism that includes a range of functions such as time-step coordination, data exchange, and simulation control. Synchronization enables the simulators to

Fig. 5. Sequence diagram of Co-zyBench.

advance the simulation at the same speed through time-step coordination, guaranteeing that data exchanges and interactions occur at the correct moments. To achieve a more flexible co-simulation that can integrate various types of simulations, our co-simulation middleware provides interfaces to support data exchange with other Python, Matlab, and Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) based simulators. The sequence diagram in Fig. 5 illustrates the overall orchestration of an experiment by the co-simulator for a given scenario and a given HVAC control system. At the beginning of the evaluation, the Evaluator (a Co-zyBench user), initiates the process by providing the thermal comfort provision system (*tc_system*) to be evaluated and the selected scenario setup (*building, people*) as inputs.

The middleware starts the building simulation to obtain building conditions (*building_info*), such as indoor and outdoor temperature and energy consumption of HVAC system components. Building information, along with simulation time (*time*) and scenarios of the occupant (*people*), are used to simulate people’s location and thermal sensations (*p_loc, p_TS*). By executing the user-provided *tc_system*, the middleware obtains the HVAC setpoints (*hvac_setpoints*) by aggregating *p_TS* based on *building_info*. These parameters are used as inputs for running the building simulation for the next time step. Additionally, the parameter *p_loc* is set in the building simulator, as our benchmark assumes the occupants to be accompanied by equipment that generates heat. This makes our simulation more realistic and takes into account the impact of occupants’ movements on the building’s energy performance. The building simulation outputs the energy consumption (*current_EC*) and update *temp_building*. To get the metrics results on occupant thermal comfort, the middleware requests the Occupant Simulator to compute *current_ITC* and *current_TCE* (see Section 5.1 for more details). Moreover, the middleware computes and collects the environmental impact based on (*current_EC*). Finally, the middleware advances the simulation time by step and the co-simulation is repeated until reaching the end of the simulation time.

5. Co-zyBench components for benchmarking

5.1. Evaluation metrics

Co-zyBench introduces five evaluation metrics that are designed to explore the impact of a diverse workforce and a sustainability focus on reducing energy consumption, as well as the thermal comfort provided to individuals.

Individual Thermal Comfort (ITC). We use the TSV scale to model thermal sensation in a 7-point scale from -3 (very cold) to 3 (very hot). Hence, the Sensation Collector in the thermal comfort provision system attempts to predict the specific value on this scale that would match the current thermal sensation of individuals. These individual predictions are then aggregated by the Sensation Aggregator into a group thermal sensation (*GTS*) which represents the overall comfort level of the group. The *GTS* is subsequently used by the HVAC Controller to determine an appropriate HVAC control action. To assess the performance of the system, we compute the difference, in absolute value, between the computed *GTS* and the real thermal sensation (*TS*) of each user. This way, this metric computes how uncomfortable an individual would feel if the system implements a temperature change based on the *GTS*. Hence, the higher this value is, the higher the discomfort the occupants would feel. Since there are multiple people and multiple spaces in the building, we aggregate this information as follows. At each round *r*, referring to a time interval or iteration during which the thermal comfort provision system makes predictions and adjustments, let the thermal sensation of *n*

people in zone z be $TS_r[z] = \{TS_r[z][1], \dots, TS_r[z][n]\}$. We define the metric, ITC , for number of people n in zones Z for all the round R as

$$ITC = \frac{\sum_{r=0}^R \sum_{z=0}^Z \sum_{i=1}^n |TS_r[z][i] - GTS_r[z]|}{\sum_{r=0}^R \sum_{z=0}^Z n} \quad (1)$$

where $GTS_r[z]$ models the computed group thermal sensation value for zone z at round r , $\sum_{r=0}^R \sum_{z=0}^Z n$ is the total number of data points. Hence, a strategy that minimizes the average discomfort that people experience will minimize the ITC value.

Thermal Comfort Equality (TCE). Even today, inequity in thermal comfort, particularly based on gender and/or age has been highlighted as a challenge that requires rethinking equality in air conditioning in buildings [58]. We propose TCE by aggregating the idea from [15]. In this work, the authors proposed a mathematical model of *fairness* in participatory thermal comfort provision based on the fairness definition for the carpooling problem [59]. The idea is to compute, each round, a notion of how much of the overall discomfort of a group, based on the group thermal sensation GTS value computed by the strategy, each individual would have to suffer to make the system fair. This value, referred to as an *Ideal Loss* (or ideal discomfort), is computed by splitting $ITC_r[z]$ equally among all the people in the zone, meaning the level of discomfort each occupant should experience in a fair scenario. Then, based on this the authors propose a notion of *Extra Loss* which compares the discomfort of one participant P_i against this ideal situation as $EL[P_i] = ITC_r[z][P_i] - \frac{ITC_r[z]}{n}$ where n is the number of participants in the zone z at round r . A positive, or negative, value for $EL[P_i]$ means that this participant had a lesser, or greater, discomfort than what would be expected if the overall discomfort of the group was shared equally. Since it would be impossible for a system to be fair in the decision made for each round, the authors also introduce the notion of *Accumulated Extra Loss* of an individual at a round r as the summation of the *Extra Loss* the individual has experienced until that round. A strategy would be “fair” if, for the n users in the zone and at the round r , their *Accumulated Extra Loss* in absolute value is bounded by some constant C which is independent of r [59].

Energy Consumption (EC). This metric represents the amount of energy consumed (in kWh) by the HVAC system to implement the decided group thermal comfort of the user’s system. Given that the HVAC Controller translates a group thermal comfort value to a temperature setpoint value for HVAC, this metric computes the required energy to achieve that setpoint for each of the zones and all of the rounds. Note that the temperature setpoint value might change in every round which means that in some specific rounds, the energy consumed might be higher than others. Specifically, suppose the group thermal comfort obtained is feeling cold. In that case, this might translate into setting up a higher setpoint than the current one which, if the HVAC is only cooling the zone, might not consume energy during that round. This metric can be measured using various real IoT devices or simulation approaches. This paper uses the widely adopted and open-source tool EnergyPlus [60] in our experimental evaluation.

Carbon Dioxide Emission (CDE). As the urgency of addressing climate change continues to grow, it is imperative to assess and reduce the environmental impact of buildings, primarily by minimizing greenhouse gas emissions. A key factor in the assessment is the fluctuation of Carbon Intensity (CI), which quantifies the amount of CO_2 emitted per kilowatt-hour (kWh) of electricity consumed [3]. CI serves as a key indicator of the environmental cost of energy consumption with lower CI values indicating cleaner, more sustainable energy sources. For example, renewable sources like solar and wind typically have a CI close to zero, whereas fossil fuels like coal and natural gas result in significantly higher CI values. CI data can often be obtained from publicly available sources. We have included data for some typical regions in the benchmark as a reference. To estimate CO_2 emissions CDE , the carbon intensity can be utilized as follows: $CDE = \sum_{r=0}^R \sum_{e=0}^E EC_r[e] * CI_r[e]$, where R is the total number of rounds and E is a set of energy generation resources. For example, renewable electricity generators within the microgrid produce energy without emitting CO_2 into the environment, thus their CI can be 0. Conversely, the CI of electricity imported from the public grid is determined by the power plants in the area. $EC_r[t]$ represents the energy consumption in kWh at round r for energy source e . $CI_r[e]$ is the carbon intensity in gCO_2/kWh for energy source e .

Overall Performance Score (OPS). We introduce a final metric that enables the direct comparison of the overall performance of different thermal comfort provision systems. This approach addresses the contradictory nature of the individual metrics and the fact that different strategies are optimized for different metrics and can hardly be fairly compared. This comparison is achieved by computing the standard score (z-score) for each strategy per metric, aggregating the scores, and comparing the results. A standard score also called a *z-score*, represents the number of standard deviations by which the value of a metric is above or below the mean value. The z-score can be calculated using the formula: $z = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma}$, where X is the result of each individual metric, μ is the mean value of the metric results and σ is the standard deviation. This value indicates if a strategy performs better (negative value) or worse (positive value) on this specific metric. Using the z-score metric, we can estimate a relative ranking of the *Overall Performance Score* (OPS) of thermal comfort provision systems by summing up the z-scores across all metrics M : $OPS = \sum_{k=1}^M z_k$. The system with a higher OPS value performs generally better.

5.2. Thermal comfort provisioning system integrator

As defined in Section 3, thermal comfort provision systems are divided into three subsystems based on their roles: the Sensation Collector collects thermal sensations, the Sensation Aggregator aggregates these sensations into a group sensation, and the HVAC Controller translates the group sensation into an HVAC control action. This division not only allows for analysis and optimization of each component but also provides users with supplemental reference subsystems for projects focused on specific subcomponents. This section introduces a set of reference subsystems, from state-of-the-art solutions, we integrated into our benchmark.

	19 °C	20 °C	21 °C	22 °C	23 °C	24 °C	25 °C	26 °C	27 °C	28 °C	29 °C
Warm Preferred	-3	-2	-2	-1	-1	0	0	0	1	1	2
Neutral	-2	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	2
Cold Preferred	-1	-1	0	0	0	1	1	2	2	3	3

Fig. 6. Three types of thermal profiles and their votes.

5.2.1. Sensation collector

Co-zyBench includes two traditional sensation collectors.

Historical data-based. This approach leverages historical thermal sensation data extracted from real building environments. In particular, we use the ASHRAE Global Thermal Comfort Database II [61], which comprises 107,463 thermal comfort samples collected over the last two decades from field studies worldwide. These samples include how people, with specific thermal profiles (such as age, gender, and activity level), felt in the environmental conditions at the recorded time. We trained a K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model to predict how an individual with a specific profile would feel given the current environmental conditions in the space [26]. The KNN model uses features of indoor temperature and occupant profiles to find the closest matches in the dataset. Consequently, this approach requires defining occupant DTs using a subset of attributes from the dataset, such as age, gender or activity level. Alternatively, users can replace the dataset with their own data for customization. This approach is also employed by the Sensation Modeler module to model thermal sensations in occupant DTs.

Prior knowledge-based. Collecting personal information poses significant difficulties and risks, such as complying with varying regulations or increasing privacy vulnerabilities. Hence, another sensation collector typically used in the field is to create heuristics [8,62,63]. In particular, in [62], the authors suggest that people have the highest productivity at a temperature of around 22 °C. A survey in [63] reports that participants generally feel comfortable when the temperature is about 23 °C. In [8], different thermal preferences are described based on gender in home and office situations. Men prefer 22 °C, and women prefer 25 °C. Hence, we implement a sensation collector that simply classifies people into three profiles based on the previous heuristics (see Fig. 6). This way, if the temperature in a particular zone is 23 °C, the sensation collected for an occupant would be -1, 1, or 0 depending on whether they prefer warm/cold temperatures or feel generally neutral.

5.2.2. Sensation aggregator

Co-zyBench includes three sensation aggregators based on state-of-the-art techniques:

Majority rule. The most traditional way to aggregate sensations for occupants in the same space is to apply a majority rule to reach a consensus. This is considered a robust rule [64] since it always satisfies the majority's requirement and maximizes the overall thermal comfort level of the occupants.

Drift approach. Purdon et al. [65] present the following aggregation strategy to provide thermal comfort while conserving energy: If the summary of the thermal sensations of a group is higher than 0 (or lower than 0) the output group thermal sensation is 2 (or -2). If the sum is zero, which means that everybody is comfortable, instead of maintaining the current temperature, they apply a *drift* towards the temperature outside of the building to save energy (e.g., representing that the group is slightly warm or cold depending on whether is winter or summer, respectively).

Fairness approach. Shin et al. [15] propose an approach to maintain *fairness* among the occupants of a building. As introduced in Section 5.1, people accumulate loss when their discomfort is greater than the ideal fair discomfort. Otherwise, they reduce their accumulated loss. For example, if the aggregated group thermal sensation is 0, people who feel warm (2 on the scale) get more loss than those who feel slightly warm (1 on the scale). To maintain fairness, the approach takes into account the accumulated loss of each individual in each round and chooses a group thermal sensation value that minimizes the accumulated loss of the individual with the highest loss so far.

5.2.3. HVAC controller

Co-zyBench includes two standard HVAC controllers:

Fixed rule-based. A straightforward approach to control the HVAC based on how fast the temperature needs to be changed to satisfy users. In particular, Co-zyBench implements the findings in [65]: typically people accept a changing temperature by 1 °C in a room in 30 min. We implement hence an approach that increases/decreases the current HVAC setpoint by 0.5 °C every 10, 15, or 30 min if the aggregated thermal sensation is -3/3, -2/2, or -1/1.

Preference estimation-based. The Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) [66] is a well-known metric that evaluates the thermal comfort level of a space. While PMV provides a broad assessment of thermal comfort, it does not account for individual variations in comfort preferences. Inspired by Gao et al. [67], who introduce an adaptation of the PMV model based on tailoring the general thermal comfort inference to individual measurements, we propose a strategy to optimize the HVAC setpoint according to the thermal comfort estimations. This strategy mainly focuses on estimating what temperature would be preferred by occupants who currently feel uncomfortable based on historical thermal comfort records. To this end, a historical dataset of occupant thermal sensations is required.

Given the current temperature T_{current} , we extract all data points from the historical dataset where the temperature is within $T_{\text{current}} \pm 1$ °C. These extracted data points are assumed to represent the range of comfort sensations occupants might experience under the current environmental conditions. We further assume these comfort levels follow a Gaussian distribution, allowing us to calculate the mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of the comfort levels:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{D} \sum_{d=1}^D tc_d, \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{D} \sum_{d=1}^D (tc_d - \mu)^2} \quad (2)$$

where tc_d represents the thermal sensation value reported in data points d (range from -3 to 3), and D is the total number of the data points.

For the current comfort level C_{current} generated by the Sensation Aggregator, we can determine its position y in the Gaussian distribution of the extracted data points. The position represents the general preference of the current people. For example, if the y falls on the left side of the distribution, it means the current occupants generally feel colder and prefer warmer than usual at the current temperature.

$$y = -\frac{C_{\text{current}} - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (3)$$

In this equation, a negative sign is introduced to invert the position, ensuring alignment with the comfort temperature adjustment process. For example, if y falls on the right side of the comfort distribution, indicating that people prefer colder than usual. Therefore, when matching temperatures, a lower-than-usual temperature should be selected, which corresponds to the left side of the $T_{\text{comfortable}}$ distribution as expressed in Eq. (4).

Next, we focus on a subset $T_{\text{comfortable}}$ of the dataset where occupants have reported being thermally comfortable, defined by sensations within the range $-0.5 \leq \text{sensation} \leq 0.5$. If the current comfort level indicates overheating ($C_{\text{current}} > 0$), we further restrict the dataset to include only temperatures lower than T_{current} ; similarly, for overcooling ($C_{\text{current}} < 0$), we consider only higher temperatures. The calculation of T_{target} involves mapping the normalized position y which represents the general preference of occupants to a specific temperature percentile within the refined dataset of comfortable temperatures:

$$T_{\text{target}} = \text{Percentile} \left(\frac{y+3}{6} \times 100, \{T_{\text{comfortable}}\} \right) \quad (4)$$

Here, position y is normalized using $y_{\text{normalized}} = \frac{y+3}{6}$ since the range of y is from -3 to 3 and this formula can normalize it to the range $[0, 1]$. The normalized y is then converted to a percentile (0% to 100%) and used to find the corresponding temperature within the comfortable temperature subset $T_{\text{comfortable}}$.

5.3. Simulation scenarios

We now introduce our reference scenarios as well as configurable approaches for Co-zyBench users to create and customize evaluation scenarios.

5.3.1. Standard scenarios

Co-zyBench includes a variety of reference scenarios such as buildings, HVAC systems, occupants, and environmental condition settings. This section presents the reference scenarios that users can reuse and override for evaluations and also introduces the methodology created for users to customize scenarios based on their data models and requirements.

Reference buildings. Co-zyBench includes a variety of buildings of different types. Firstly, we designed a model of an office building. Fig. 7(a) shows the floor plan of the office space with a gross conditioning area of 371 m³. The common areas (i.e., conference rooms, break room, kitchen, and restroom) are shared by different people at different points in time while the office rooms are shared by workers who are assigned to specific workplaces.

In addition, our benchmark includes a widely used set of reference buildings developed by the U.S. Department of Energy (DoE) which approximately covers 70% of commercial buildings in the USA [68]. From the DoE buildings, we select those with public regions that highly require thermal comfort provision systems for individual occupants, such as offices, hotels, hospitals, and school buildings as shown in Fig. 7(b). These buildings vary in overall size and room dimensions depending on their type. Rooms are designed with specific functions. For example, office buildings include shared open spaces, small private offices, and meeting rooms. The function of each room corresponds to the roles and activities of occupants, as defined in occupant DTs. For instance, employees in office buildings typically work in shared open offices, while managers use private offices for work. Table 1 shows the configurations of the selected DOE buildings, including their area size, number of floors, and number of zones.

Reference environmental conditions. The environmental condition is modeled based on the locations of these buildings which span different climate zones to ensure comprehensive evaluation. We have included several cities' latest available Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) weather reports, derived from the most recent 15 years (2007–2021), to represent the typical weather of each city. The weather files are in EPW format, sourced from [69]. Secondly, based on the climate zone classification, we modeled construction sets for different climates across all climate zones according to the ASHRAE 189.1-2009 standard [70]. These construction sets define the building materials and insulation levels suitable for various climates. Table 2 showcases some of the integrated cities and their corresponding construction information, highlighting how insulation properties and thermal characteristics are tailored to specific

Fig. 7. Sample reference buildings included in Co-zyBench.

Table 1
Settings of the DOE buildings.

Building type	Area (m ²)	Floors	Zones
Small office	510.97	1	6
Medium office	4 983.22	3	18
Large office	46 314.19	12	72
Primary school	6871.80	1	25
Secondary school	19 585.89	2	46
Small hotel	4 011.06	4	67
Large hotel	11 344.45	6	22
Hospital	22 420.45	5	55

Table 2
Building properties for different climate zones.

City	ASHRAE CZ	Insulation external wall	Conductivity of windows	Insulation of roof
Mumbai	Extreme hot humid	3.4 cm	2.1 W/mK	17 cm
Cairo	Hot dry	4.5 cm	0.042 W/mK	21 cm
LA	Warm dry	5.6 cm	0.019 W/mK	21 cm
Paris	Mixed humid	6.8 cm	0.013 W/mK	21 cm
Scranton	Cool humid	7.9 cm	0.013 W/mK	21 cm

ASHRAE Climate Zones (CZ). For example, cities in cooler climates, such as Paris (Cool Humid), feature thicker insulation materials compared to cities in warmer climates like Mumbai (Extreme Hot Humid). Finally, we include historical datasets of carbon intensity into the benchmarking tool for the regions introduced in Table 2 for the period 2023 to 2024. This dataset provides information on the carbon intensity of the energy used in each location, allowing users to evaluate the environmental impact of their thermal comfort provision systems. The data includes hourly values for one year, sourced from *electricityMap*.¹ Due to the impracticality of including data for every city, we encourage users to integrate additional environmental setups to supplement their evaluations.

Reference HVAC systems. To cover a wider range of climate conditions and building types, we provide three HVAC system types for users to select: Constant Air Volume (CAV), Variable Air Volume (VAV), and Variable Refrigerant Flow (VRF) systems (see Fig. 8). Each system has unique characteristics and is suitable for different types of buildings. The CAV system has the simplest design, delivering a constant air volume to thermal zones with only one temperature setpoint to all zones. It is mainly consisting of an outdoor air (OA) system, an Air Handling Unit (AHU), sensors, and air terminals. The mixture of the return and outdoor air from the OA system is delivered to thermal zones and conditioned by the AHU on the way to a zone. The controller supervises the supply air temperature in the duct and operates the coils in AHU to control the pressure and temperature of the supply air. The VAV system is similar to the CAV system but with variable air volume control to achieve precise temperature control for different zones of the building. Finally, VRF systems are advanced HVAC solutions that provide precise temperature control and energy efficiency by varying the flow of refrigerant to multiple indoor units. In summary, CAV systems are suitable for small buildings with a single zone, while VAV and VRF are suitable for large buildings where energy efficiency and precise control are important. Co-zyBench users can select one of the systems for their evaluations based on the type and size of their buildings, or define their HVAC systems with customized settings.

Reference occupant. Here we introduce two types of occupant scenarios which are also the counterpart to the occupant profile modeling approaches provided by Co-zyBench. The occupant profile modeling approaches should match with the Sensation Collector

¹ <https://www.electricitymaps.com>, accessed July 2024.

Fig. 8. Three types of reference HVAC systems in Co-zyBench.

Office	Name	Gender	Job	Age	Height	Weight
Office Small	Michael	male	Boss	51	175	2
Office Large	Erin	female	Receptionist	33	165	2
	Jim	male	Seller	33	191	1
	Dwight	male	Seller	47	189	2
	Pam	female	Seller	39	168	1
	Andy	male	Seller	39	182	2
	Stanley	male	Seller	55	180	3
	Phyllis	female	Seller	64	166	2
	Oscar	male	Accountant	54	175	1
Kevin	male	Accountant	40	185	3	
Angela	female	Accountant	42	155	2	
Meredith	female	Supplier Manager	49	163	3	
Creed	female	None	70	183	3	
Office Medium	Toby	male	HR	46	177	1
	Gabe	male	Marketing	29	193	1
	Clark	male	Customer Service	28	175	1
	Pete	male	Customer Service	28	177	1
	Kelly	female	Sales Representative	34	163	1

TIME	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
9:00					
9:30	Boss, Sellers				
10:00		Sellers	Boss, Accountants, Supplier Manager	Sellers	
10:30	Sellers, Marketing, Sales Representative				Sellers, Marketing, Sales Representative.
11:00					
11:30					
12:00 - 14:00	Lunch Time				
14:00					
14:30	Accounts		Sellers, Marketing, Sales Representative.		All
15:00					
15:30					

(a) Occupant Profile

(b) Meeting Schedule

Fig. 9. Occupant information for the reference office building.

to estimate occupant thermal sensations based on the modeled occupant profiles. The first kind of reference occupant scenario is built based on personal profile data for both estimating movement trajectories and thermal sensations. For example, for the office building introduced above, we created 18 different occupants for the experiment with diverse profiles (see Fig. 9(a)), including static information such as their jobs and working offices, which can be used to predict their activities and location. Additionally, their gender, age, height, and weight (abstracted to Body Mass Index categories) can be used to model their thermal preferences. Fig. 9(b) shows the meeting schedules used to simulate their trajectories. People start working in the building at around 9 am and leave after 6 pm. People spend most of their working time attending a “working event” that occurs in their assigned offices. Their schedule of weekly and daily events involves two types of meetings happening in the conference room: small meetings, held by some members of one or two teams mainly in the morning lasting 30 to 60 min; and large meetings, held by some members of two or more teams lasting around 90 min. For example, sellers and marketers have a small meeting every two days for at most one hour in the morning, all the staff have a large meeting at 14:00 for at most two hours every Friday. Besides, we model a lunchtime event from 12:00 to 14:00 and limit the amount of time spent for lunch to around one hour in the kitchen, the break room, or the outside. Moreover, people also attend non-time-fixed events like taking a break in the break room and going to the restroom.

We also create other occupant scenarios for buildings where personal private information collection is not feasible. We first decide how many people should be in the building based on the building type and the guideline provided by the NFPA 101: Life Safety Code 2018 [71], which limits the occupants in offices, factories, and workrooms should be lower than one person per 14 square meters. We create people with different identities as shown in Table 3. Based on the type of building, we create different events for each type of occupant. For example, in office buildings, employees have random meetings every day with some of the managers, and other staff such as service and technical support personnel can go to any of the rooms at any time.

Table 3
Occupant profiles and distribution for the DOE reference buildings.

Office	m ² /Person 15	Employee (%) 0.7	Manager (%) 0.2	Other Staff (%) 0.1
School	m ² /Person 10	Student (%) 0.7	Teacher (%) 0.2	Admin (%) 0.1
Hotel	m ² /Person 30	Customer (%) 0.8	Staff (%) 0.15	Manager (%) 0.05
Hospital	m ² /Person 20	Patient (%) 0.5	Doctor (%) 0.3	Other Staff (%) 0.2

Table 4
Diversity scenarios.

Scenario	%cold	%neutral	%warm
No majority (<i>NM</i>)	40	20	40
Majority cold 1 (<i>MC80</i>)	80	0	20
Majority cold 2 (<i>MC70</i>)	70	0	30
Majority warm 1 (<i>MW80</i>)	20	0	80
Majority warm 2 (<i>MW70</i>)	30	0	70

On the other hand, in cases where personal data is not accessible, we model occupant thermal profiles using the *Prior Knowledge-Based* approach to categorize each occupant as having a cold, warm, or neutral preference. While it is still not clear what a realistic distribution of different preferred occupants would be. This not only changes from one country to another but even from one job sector or even specific workplace to another within a country. Hence, we create five different diversity scenarios for the buildings. [Table 4](#) shows the different scenarios in terms of the distribution of people who prefer colder/warmer temperatures and people who are mostly neutral. As explained before, the preference towards colder/warmer temperatures could be associated with people from different genders, ages, body compositions, ethnicity, etc. We introduced scenarios where there is a clear majority of one preference or the other to showcase better the challenges that arise in terms of providing thermal comfort to individuals while maintaining fairness.

5.3.2. Scalable and configurable scenarios

Co-zyBench users may want to evaluate thermal comfort provision systems in other scenarios beyond the reference ones. For instance, they might want to evaluate them in their own buildings/DTs or in synthetic buildings satisfying certain restrictions (e.g., with a very large number of occupants per space or with a very large number of rooms). Co-zyBench supports two easy-to-use mechanisms to enable users to define these requirements:

- *DT importer tool*. The tool parses an NGSi-LD formatted building and occupant DT to extract essential attributes, as introduced in Section 4. This data is mapped to the simulation model, then validation checks are conducted to ensure completeness, and default values are filled in if necessary. For the occupant model, the data will be converted into two simulation models: one for simulating occupant movement trajectories and another for thermal sensation estimation.
- *Synthetic scenario generation tool*. Users need only to provide this tool with inputs such as the number of floors, rooms, windows, and occupants to generate a synthetic building DT. Then, users need to select one of the occupant thermal patterns in [Tables 3](#) and [4](#) to create a synthetic occupant DT. [Algorithm 2](#) showcases the process of generating the synthetic scenario. First, it estimates the proper size of the building, based on the inputted numbers of floors and rooms, and generates its shape (line 1). The building will be divided equally into floors (line 2). Next, a recursive algorithm will be used to divide the largest space on each floor into the desired number of rooms (line 5) and generate the room models with missing information such as room capacity (line 6). Finally, exterior windows and doors will be assigned to the rooms based on the inputted number of them. Occupants are generated based on the input number, occupant scenario and thermal distribution (line 14). Finally, the building and occupant models are formatted in NGSi-LD with default setups such as construction materials (line 12, 15), and the previously developed NGSi-LD parser tool is used to create the DTs (line 16).

6. Experimental evaluation

We showcase our benchmark by evaluating the performance of reference thermal comfort provision systems in different scenarios. Our ultimate goal is to assess the impact of occupant thermal preference diversity and climate zone on the performance of the systems (measured using the Co-zyBench's metrics).

Algorithm 2 Synthetic scenario generation.**Input:** Number of floors F , rooms R , windows W , doors D , occupant O , occupant scenario S , thermal comfort distribution Dis **Output:** Digital Twin models M for building and occupant

```

1:  $building\_envelope = generate\_building(F, R)$ 
2:  $floors = split\_building(building\_envelope, F)$ 
3: for each  $f$  in  $floors$  do
4:    $floor\_models = generate\_floor(building\_envelope, f)$ 
5:    $rooms = split\_floor(floor\_models, R)$ 
6:    $room\_models = generate\_room(floor\_models, rooms)$ 
7:   for each  $r$  in  $rooms$  do
8:      $windows = generate\_windows(position\_rooms, W)$ 
9:      $doors = generate\_doors(position\_rooms, Dis)$ 
10:  end for
11: end for
12:  $building\_model = generate\_ngsild(floor\_models, room\_models, windows, doors)$ 
13:  $occupant\_nums = cal\_occ\_number(building\_envelope, S)$ 
14:  $occupant = assign\_thermal\_preference(occupant, D)$ 
15:  $occupant\_model = generate\_ngsild(occupant, room\_models)$ 
16:  $M = dt\_importer(building\_model, occupant\_model)$ 
17: return  $M$ 

```

6.1. Experimental setup

We describe the experimental setup in terms of thermal comfort provision systems and scenarios used for evaluation. The experiments focus the evaluation on workdays in months of the year where most energy consumption takes place and adapt the HVAC system to perform: cooling in summer and heating in winter (132 days in total). We run the benchmark for each thermal comfort provision system five times and average the results.

6.1.1. Thermal comfort provision systems

We evaluate various combinations of Co-zyBench's state-of-the-art Sensation Collectors, Sensation Aggregators, and HVAC Controllers introduced previously. These combinations are denoted using three letters XYZ to represent the thermal comfort provision system. The first letter (X) signifies the sensation collector, which can be H for *Historical Data-Based* or P for *Prior Knowledge-Based*. The second letter (Y) represents the sensation aggregator, which can vary, including F for *Fairness Approach*, D for *Drift Approach*, or M for *Majority*. The third letter (Z) denotes the HVAC controller, which can be F for *Fixed Rule-Based* or P for *Preference Estimation-Based*. For instance, HFF means a system that utilizes a *Historical Data-Based* sensation collector, a *Fairness* sensation aggregator, and a *Fixed Rule-Based* HVAC controller. We also include a baseline system for comparison, denoted as HCC , which uses a *Historical Data-Based* approach to estimate thermal sensations but disregards the explicit thermal sensation of the occupants, setting a constant temperature of 23 °C, considered favorable for a group of people [63].

In addition, for each HXF system, we evaluate two sensation collection assumptions:

1. **Assumption 1:** individuals employ their smartphones or a website to convey their thermal comfort sensation.
2. **Assumption 2:** sensors monitor the occupants to obtain information about their profile and current activity, and estimate their sensation based on it.

We consider that often individuals do not convey their preferences and sensor-based systems fail (either because of wrong sensor readings or inaccurate interpretation) and not all individual features can be obtained. We model this by defining four versions of each system, denoted as HXF_{100}^{AY} , HXF_{75}^{AY} , HXF_{50}^{AY} , HXF_{25}^{AY} , and HXF_0^{AY} , where A in AY represents an Assumption and Y its number (Assumption 1 or 2). In particular, the number in the subscript for $A1$ corresponds to scenarios where 0%–100% of users actively provide feedback through their smartphones. For $A2$ it corresponds to situations where the system accurately estimates 0%–100% of the required features for thermal sensation prediction. For instance, HMF_{50}^{A1} represents a system using a majority-based aggregation approach based on comfort sensation data directly input by users in which only 50% of them give feedback. Similarly, HDF_{75}^{A2} represents a system using a drift-based aggregation approach based on comfort sensation estimation using sensors in which only 75% of the individual features (e.g., their activity level, gender, and age but not weight) can be estimated.

6.1.2. Scenarios

We evaluate thermal comfort provision systems in the following four scenarios: (1) the office building reference scenario included in Co-zyBench; (2) a customized scenario defined by the user based on a real-world building; (3) a synthetic mid-sized building created by the synthetic scenario generation tool; (4) a large-sized building created by the synthetic building generation tool.

Scenario 1: Reference office building. We choose the office building scenario, presented in Section 5.3.1, which includes 18 occupants with diverse profiles. We also select a Variable Air Volume (VAV) HVAC system where each office and conference room constitutes an individual thermal zone. Finally, to analyze the impact of climate zone in the results, we select the reference environmental configurations (i.e., weather, carbon intensity, and building construction) for the cities of Mumbai (India), Los Angeles (US), Paris (France), and Scranton (US).

Scenario 2: Real building. The second evaluation scenario involves a DT model of a real-world building: the Drahi-X Novation Center of IP Paris (see Fig. 10). The center, which spans an area of over 5000 m², includes approximately 100 small office rooms with flexible seating for 2 to 7 people, several meeting rooms, restrooms, and a 200 m² lecture hall. The building's model was initially shown in Computer-Aided Design (CAD) format, which is widely used in architectural and engineering design with design workflows. From this CAD file, we generate the corresponding Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) file, which is another standard format extensively adopted in the construction and BIM domain for its ability to provide semantic descriptions. This process can be achieved through various approaches [72], which we do not elaborate on here. Finally, we converted the IFC file into an NGS-1D format using the method described in [73]. A snippet of the resulting building NGS-1D representation is shown below:

```

1  [{
2     "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:Building:drahix:building-id",
3     "type": "Building",
4     "HasSpace": {
5         "type": "Relationship",
6         "object": [
7             "urn:ngsi-ld:Space:space-id",
8             .....
9         ]
10    }.....
11  }]
12  [{
13     "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:Space:drahix:space-id",
14     "type": "Space",
15     "relativePosition": {
16         "type": "Property",
17         "value": {
18             "type": "Trimesh",
19             "measurementUnit": "m",
20             "Dimensions": "3D",
21             "coordinates": [
22                 [-38, 34, 0],
23                 .....
24             ],
25             "faces": [
26                 [1, 0, 3],
27                 .....
28             ]
29         }
30     }
31     "hasWindow": {
32         "type": "Relationship",
33         "object": [
34             "urn:ngsi-ld:Window:drahix>window-id",
35             .....
36         ]
37     }
38     .....
39  }.....
40  ]

```

For the HVAC system, we selected a VRF system, which is used in real buildings. This system contains one outdoor unit and indoor units for each thermal zone. The system's gross rated total cooling and heating capacity is set to auto-size, which is automatically decided by the building size and the overall climate condition of the location. The system operates with a high Coefficient of Performance (CoP) of 3.3 for cooling and 3.5 for heating to ensure efficient energy use, and it is designed to function within a condenser inlet temperature range of -5 °C to 43 °C in cooling mode.

Due to privacy concerns, we rely on the approach described in Section 5.3.1 to create synthetic occupant models for 160 occupants (based on the average number of observed occupants in the building). We assigned to occupants different profiles based on Table 3, so that 96 people work as employees; 48 people as managers; and 16 as general purpose staff, with office rooms in different parts of the building. Each person works in the building from 8 am to 7 pm, Monday to Friday, and attends daily "meetings" taking place in different conference rooms and the lecture hall with around 20 to 100 people. Finally, we assign to occupants different thermal preferences according to the No Majority (NM), Majority Cold (MC70, MC80), and Majority Warm (MW70, MW80) scenarios (see Table 4). Hence, we evaluate five versions of Scenario 2 where each has a different distribution of occupant thermal preferences.

Fig. 10. Digital twin model of the Drahi-X novation center.

(a) Mid-size building.

(b) Large-size building.

Fig. 11. Example configurable synthetic building models.

Scenario 3: Mid-sized. Synthetic DT The third evaluation scenario involves synthetic building and occupant DT models created with user inputs. For this scenario, we configured Co-zyBench to generate for us a mid-sized office building (see Fig. 11(a)) with the following inputs: four floors, five rooms per floor (each room measuring $4\text{ m} \times 5\text{ m}$), one window in each room, and 25 occupants in total. Also, we configure the occupants with random thermal profiles (such as their age, gender, weight level, and activity level), and we select the environmental setup (i.e., parameters for construction materials and weather) for Paris. According to the size of the building, we also select a Variable Air Volume (VAV) HVAC system.

Scenario 4: Large-sized synthetic DT. The fourth evaluation scenario mirrors the setup of Scenario 3 but scales it up to a large-sized office building (see Fig. 11(b)). In this scenario, the synthetic DT models a building with 10 floors and 15 rooms per floor, where each room measures $8\text{ m} \times 10\text{ m}$ and includes one window. The building accommodates 1200 occupants, each assigned random thermal profiles. Similarly to Scenario 3, the environmental settings are configured for Paris.

6.1.3. Other configurations

When simulating the HVAC system, Co-zyBench controls it on a temperature setpoint where the HVAC system is switched on if it receives a demand from the thermal comfort provision system. To further increase realism, two additional considerations are added to each scenario evaluated: (1) In the real world, most building administrators decide to pre-condition the space one hour prior to peoples' arrival at the office if the temperature is too high/low. This keeps the space between $19\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $28\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the time when people arrive at the office. Note that, in some cities and some specific dates, the temperature is already in that setpoint range which means that the HVAC system does not need to pre-condition the building. (2) We include the heat produced by people located in a particular space of the building into the computation. We define that each person has a fraction radiant of 0.3 and is accompanied by electrical equipment with a power of 200 W and a fraction radiant of 0.5 [74].

6.2. Analysis of the results

This section presents the most representative portion of the results obtained focusing on the 13 most popular thermal comfort provision systems (out of the 22 supported by Co-zyBench). We structure the analysis in six parts:

1. Impact of inaccurate thermal sensation estimation on Individual Thermal Comfort (*ITC*) and Thermal Comfort Equality (*TCE*).
2. Impact of climate zone on Energy Consumption (*EC*) and Carbon Dioxide Emissions (*CDE*).
3. Impact of diversity of inhabitants on *ITC* and *TCE*.
4. Comparison of different thermal comfort provision systems based on the Overall Performance Score (*OPS*).
5. Impact of the size of the building on thermal comfort provision systems' performance.
6. Impact of unexpected building/occupant changes to performance.

Analysis 1: Impact of inaccurate thermal sensation estimation.

Fig. 12. Individual Thermal comfort (ITC).

Ensuring active participation from users in feedback-based thermal comfort provision systems poses a considerable challenge as individuals may not always have time or willingness to engage with the system. Similarly, achieving accurate thermal sensation estimation based on sensor data can be problematic due to potential sensor failures or the acquisition of inaccurate information. In this analysis, we aim to compare the thermal discomfort experienced by individuals when the previous issues arise. In particular, the following shows the results for the different *HXF* thermal comfort provision systems in *Scenario 1* (i.e., office space).

Fig. 12 shows the results in terms of Individual Thermal Comfort (*ITC*), defined in Section 5.1, where higher values represent higher occupant discomfort. Since HXF_0^{A1} and HXF_0^{A2} represent the extreme situation in which both systems fail to estimate the thermal sensation of the occupants, they always set the temperature in the spaces to 23 °C degrees which is comfortable for most people [8]. Hence, they perform the same regardless of the aggregation strategy used. This can serve as a baseline indicator since an *ITC* value below it means that at least some of the thermal comfort preferences of the occupants are considered. We observe that, as expected, using the majority rule to aggregate the thermal sensations of the group (i.e., *HMF*) outperforms all the other strategies by maintaining the lowest *ITC* value (since the *ITC* value is lower when the group comfort value computed is the median of occupants’ thermal sensations). In our scenario, like in many real buildings, most people have similar thermal preferences even if there is a minority that differs. The fairness aggregation approach (i.e., *HFF*), which sometimes introduces discomfort to a large number of people to satisfy the requirements of the minority, and the Drift Approach, which sometimes disregards all thermal preferences to lower energy consumption, as expected perform worse. As we will see next, this is a trade-off with how fair and energy efficient such aggregation strategies are.

While the results for both assumptions on how the thermal sensation is obtained/estimated are similar, we observe that Assumption 2, which predicts thermal sensation based on estimated parameters such as occupant’s age/weight/height and activity level collected through sensors, obtains slightly worse results than Assumption 1 for most of the scenarios. This is due to the challenge of predicting thermal sensation vs. directly requesting this information from users. As expected, we also observe that having more information on occupants to model their thermal sensations can have a positive effect on thermal comfort. However, in Assumption 1, using the fairness and drift (i.e., *HDF*) approaches makes occupants feel more comfortable when fewer people participate. The rationale for this outcome is evident: using these two algorithms yields worse results compared to not considering occupant comfort at all. Hence, having fewer occupants’ feedback can make more people feel comfortable but this simultaneously undermines their advantages of achieving equality and saving energy.

Different studies have highlighted the lack of equality and consideration for minorities in thermal comfort provision [15,75]. Next, we analyze the performance of the thermal comfort provision systems w.r.t. the Thermal Comfort Equality (*TCE*) metric (defined in Section 5.1). Fig. 13 shows the results for *Scenario 1* so that they can be compared with the ones in the previous analysis. The figure plots *TCE* values at the end of the experiment for all individuals in each simulation as box plots displaying the minimum, maximum, median, and first and third quartiles. The more decentralized the data is plotted, the more “unfair” the thermal comfort provision is (a value of zero for all people would be the ideal *TCE* where all discomfort was equally distributed among people).

We can clearly see that the fairness-based system, as expected, obtains the best results overall since it was designed with this goal in mind. The minimum standard deviation of the *TCE* of all the experiments using the fairness system is around 1.4 while for other systems it increases to 146 and 28 for drift and majority-based, respectively. This highlights how “unfair” the latter systems are w.r.t. some specific individuals who happen to be in the minority consistently throughout their working day. The analysis of the results also reveals that the fairness-based system performs significantly worse in the 25% scenarios (i.e., experiments, where only 25% of the users give feedback about their thermal preferences or the system, is only able to infer 25% of the user features used to estimate their preferences). This highlights that even a fairness-based thermal comfort provision system needs enough user participation and/or accurate sensing systems to infer what the preferences of the minority are.

Analysis 2: Impact of Climate Zone.

Next, we turn our attention to the impact of climate zones on systems’ energy consumption and carbon emissions. In the following, we again show the analysis of the results for Scenario 1 (i.e., office space) focusing on systems *HFF*, *HDF*, *HMF*, and *HCC*. To

Fig. 13. Thermal Comfort Equality (TCE).

Fig. 14. Energy Consumption and carbon emissions in different cities.

isolate the impact of climate zone, we consider here thermal comfort provision systems where all individuals give feedback and/or sensor-based thermal estimation is able to accurately estimate thermal sensation for all occupants (i.e., HXF_{100}^{A1} and HXF_{100}^{A2}). Finally, since some climates do not require much heating over the winter (e.g., the Extreme Hot Humid Mumbai), we focus the analysis just on the three summer months to make the comparison of the systems fair.

Figs. 14 and 14(a) plot the Energy Consumption (EC) and Carbon Emissions (CDE) results per city, respectively. We can observe an expected and clear difference in actual consumption and carbon emissions between warmer and colder climate zones (e.g., Mumbai vs. Paris). When focusing on specific strategies, we observe the high price that HCC pays. This is because, without occupants’ feedback, it regulates the HVAC system even if the space is empty. Of course, increasing the fixed temperature further would reduce energy consumption but would have a clear impact on both the fairness and thermal comfort of individuals. As expected, the drift-based system (i.e., HDF) outperforms the others since it is designed to consume less energy. However, note that the difference in terms of CDE is negligible for cities like Paris and Los Angeles. This is because while the carbon intensity in Mumbai is stable throughout the day with values around 700 gCO₂/kWh, in Paris carbon intensity fluctuates and is the lowest ranging from 3 to 127 gCO₂/kWh primarily because a significant portion of electricity in France is generated by nuclear plants that do not produce direct carbon dioxide emissions. Carbon intensity in Los Angeles and Scranton also fluctuates during the day, ranging from 54 to 331 gCO₂/kWh and from 245 to 425 gCO₂/kWh, respectively.

Analysis 3: Impact of occupant diversity.

The workforce is becoming more diverse worldwide and that presents benefits and challenges [76]. In our context, more diversity among occupants could lead to greater challenges in achieving thermal comfort due to the variation in the thermal preferences distributions. We next explore the impact on the performance of the different thermal comfort provision systems of an increasingly diverse workforce. In the following, we show the analysis for Scenario 2 (i.e., real-world building Drahi-X) with PFF, PDF and PMF since it will enable us to discuss some interesting contrasts between this scenario and the results presented before.

Fig. 15 presents the evaluation results in terms of ITC and TCE for the five diversity distributions in Co-zyBench (see Table 4). Note that diversity does not impact significantly the performance of the systems w.r.t. ITC (see Fig. 15(a)). With more people preferring colder temperatures, the ITC value slightly decreases. This is because we use Paris’s climate for this scenario, where the cooling demand in summer is not as high compared to the heating demand in winter. Hence, there is a greater chance of having a low indoor temperature which makes people who prefer colder environments feel comfortable. When analyzing TCE (see Fig. 15(b)²), we observe that in all diversity scenarios, the majority-based system performs much worse than the drift and fairness counterparts. This contrasts the results in our previous analysis based on the office space where the majority-based approach clearly outperformed the drift one. This is because the Drahi-X building has more occupants that tend to meet in larger spaces (e.g., the conference room)

² Note that we merged the two diversity distributions with a clear majority of Warm/Cold preferred to make the figure simpler.

Fig. 15. Thermal Comfort Equality (TCE).

Table 5
Overall Performance Scores (OPS) of the systems.

		Fairness	Drift	Majority
ITC	Fixed rule-based	0.62 (-0.01)	0.97 (-1.22)	0.26 (1.22)
	Preference estimation-based	0.62 (-0.01)	0.97 (-1.22)	0.25 (1.23)
TCE	Fixed rule-based	1.56 (1.41)	57.97 (-0.59)	66.00 (-0.88)
	Preference Estimation-Based	1.77 (1.40)	58.32 (-0.60)	62.16 (-0.74)
EC	Fixed rule-based	725.81 (-1.03)	702.77 (-0.04)	730.31 (-1.22)
	Preference estimation-based	689.37 (0.54)	660.51 (1.78)	702.73 (-0.03)
OPS	Fixed rule-based	0.38	-1.85	-0.87
	Preference estimation-based	1.93	-0.05	0.46

compared to the small office space. Hence, there is a higher likelihood of more people with the same preference being in a space than a small number of people with a different preference which exacerbates the “unfairness” of the majority-based system. As expected, the fairness-based system outperforms all the other systems but, compared to the results obtained for the office space, its performance is not as good in situations where there is no clear majority. This is due to the fact that the Drahi-X building scenario has more complex dynamics, characterized by intricate building structures and complicated occupant movements, which presents challenges to maintaining fairness.

Analysis 4: Overall performance and system selection.

As the previous analysis has shown, choosing the “best” thermal comfort provision system is challenging because of their strengths and weaknesses in different aspects. Our benchmark introduces an Overall Performance Score (OPS) metric for this purpose. Next, we analyze the OPS results obtained for Scenario 3 (i.e., synthetic building dynamically generated). We evaluate the three Sensation Aggregators (Fairness, Drift, Majority) with two HVAC Controllers (HFF, HDF, HMF, HFP, HDP and HMP) on the overall performance across ITC, TCE and EC.

Table 5 shows the z-score of each metric for each system. OPS is the summary of the z-scores where a higher value means it outperforms the average performance. From the results, we can observe that using the Preference Estimation-based approach is generally better than using the Fixed Rule-based approach. The Preference Estimation-based approach can achieve better performance in energy conservation while maintaining equivalent comfort levels. Additionally, although the Fairness approach primarily focuses on TCE, its performance on the other metrics is not poor, making it the best sensation aggregator according to the overall performance. This suggests that utilizing the Fairness approach along with the Preference Estimation-based approach is the optimal solution for this building and occupant scenarios of the scalable model.

Analysis 5: Impact of the size of the building.

This analysis focuses on the performance of the baseline systems when the size of the building increases. Specifically, we compare their performance on two synthetic DTs: Scenario 3 (mid-sized) and Scenario 4 (large-sized). These DTs share identical environmental and occupant thermal profile configurations, with the primary difference being the size of the building and the number of occupants. As demonstrated in Analysis 4, the Preference Estimation-Based approach generally outperforms the Fixed Rule-Based approach as an HVAC controller. Based on this finding, we select the Preference Estimation-Based approach for the HVAC controller and proceed to evaluate systems HFP, HDP, and HMP.

The comparison of system performance in the two scenarios is shown in Table 6. The values in the table represent the results for the corresponding metrics, with the values in parentheses under the large-sized synthetic DT indicating the percentage change or difference compared to the mid-sized synthetic DT. For example, the HFP system performs 1.48 times worse on ITC in the Large-sized scenario. Based on Table 6, the energy consumption (EC) in larger buildings is approximately 130 times higher than that of mid-sized buildings. This result is expected, as the HVAC system needs to manage a significantly larger area and a higher number of occupants. For the other metrics, the most interesting finding is that the performance of the HFP system degrades significantly

Table 6
System performance in different sized scenarios.

		HFP	HDP	HMP
Mid-sized synthetic DT	ITC	0.62	0.97	0.25
	TCE	1.77	58.32	62.16
	EC	689.37	660.51	702.73
Large-sized synthetic DT	ITC	1.54 (1.48)	0.71 (-0.27)	0.08 (-0.68)
	TCE	2.57 (0.45)	34.60 (-0.41)	12.77 (-0.79)
	EC	89240.97 (128)	92169.97 (138)	88690.63 (125)

Table 7
System performance deviation when the scenario changes.

		HFP	HDP	HMP
10 floors, 1200 occupants	ITC	1.54	0.71	0.08
	TCE	2.57	34.60	12.77
	EC	89 240.97	92 169.97	88 690.63
10 floors, 800 occupants	ITC	1.61	0.72	0.04
	TCE	1.68	14.65	7.04
	EC	89 134.79	92 098.03	88 605.91
8 floors, 1200 occupants	ITC	1.50	0.71	0.08
	TCE	2.05	29.67	10.69
	EC	72 356.42	74 699.37	72 279.13

in large buildings compared to mid-sized buildings, whereas the other systems show improved performance in large buildings. This result directly highlights the importance of evaluating the system under different scenarios, as different systems may perform better or worse in specific contexts. Additionally, this analysis strongly demonstrates the scalability of our system, including its capability to generate scenarios of varying scales and effectively evaluate performance across these different scales.

Analysis 6: Impact of unexpected building/occupant changes to performance.

In this analysis, we rely on Scenario 4, the large-sized synthetic building with 1200 occupants and we assume unexpected changes that might impact the performance of thermal comfort provision systems. For instance, certain areas in the building need to be closed for construction or a number of employees start working remotely. To this end, we evaluate two scenarios: (1) Closing two floors and (2) Decreasing the number of occupants to 800. We focus the analysis on the following baselines: *HFP*, *HDP* and *HMP*.

The evaluation results are shown in Table 7. First, we observe in all three thermal comfort provision systems that energy consumption (*EC*) remains similar when the number of occupants decreases. This is because, in this scenario, even though the number of occupants decreases from 1200 to 800, the overall spatial distribution of occupants remains largely unchanged, leading to a similar level of space utilization. Also, when only 8 floors are accessible, *EC* reduces to approximately 80%, as expected. Even though this result might seem obvious, keep in mind that when floors are closed the HVAC system has to still function to a minimum rate. This result, along with the fact that the number of occupants remains the same, shows that most of the *EC* goes into maintaining the temperature of the occupied spaces. The thermal comfort provision systems perform similarly in terms of *ITC* across different setups, except for the *HMP* system which performs better under fewer occupants. This is because of the reduced likelihood of individuals with diverse preferences sharing the same space when occupant numbers are lower. In addition, when the number of occupants decreases the systems show better performance in terms of *TCE*.

Discussion.

After analyzing the results, it becomes evident that each thermal comfort provision system has its advantages. In the case of the Sensation Collector system, Assumption 1 outperforms Assumption 2 when compared at the same percentage level. However, since Assumption 2's standout feature is its independence from the participation of people, in the real world one would expect to compare the systems at different percentage levels (e.g., HXF_{50}^{A1} vs. HXF_{75}^{A2}) which makes the results closer. Among the three Sensation Aggregators we assessed, each system excels in the feature it has been designed to optimize: overall thermal comfort for Majority Rule (MR), equality for the Fairness Approach (FA), and energy consumption and CO2 emissions for the Drift Approach (DA). However, note that when looking at the overall performance across metrics, even when there is no clear winner, FA achieves a good tradeoff in performance. We have also shown that these results are highly dependent on the building and occupant scenarios and could be different in situations where there is a different distribution of thermal preferences, building size and occupant pattern. Co-ZyBench supports executing experiments in variations of a scenario which makes it possible, with a small configuration change, to evaluate the performance of the presented (or any other system) in multiple configurations which would be infeasible to do otherwise.

6.3. Threats to validity

This section introduces internal and external threats to validity that may impact the reliability of our Co-zyBench.

Internal Validity. As described in Section 3.3, Co-zyBench utilizes simulators for the occupants and buildings. Even though the simulators have proven their effectiveness, they are based on a limited set of parameters that may not fully capture the complexity of

Fig. 16. Accuracy of energy consumption estimation across different outdoor temperatures.

real-world conditions. Such inconsistencies between DTs and their counterparts potentially affect the accuracy of occupant movement modeling and energy simulations. However, due to the inherent limitation of current techniques, some level of deviation between simulated outcomes and real-world conditions is unavoidable. To mitigate this effect, we utilize simulators that have demonstrated their realism to make sure the simulation accuracy: EnergyPlus [77], a widely recognized and extensively used building simulation tool, and SmartSPEC [57], which has proven effective for simulating occupant movement trajectories.

On the other hand, we made every effort to base the estimations and data used in our simulations on credible references. Bias might be pronounced by the synthetic scenario generation tool since it only takes simple input data for modeling the simulations. However, the primary intention behind the creation of this approach is to trade off a certain degree of realism in exchange for scalability and the ability to rapidly construct models for various scenarios. We propose the use of DTs that can incorporate real-world data. Users also have the flexibility to employ their own DT models if preferred. For users seeking highly realistic simulations, we recommend calibrating their building DT models to mitigate these deviations between simulations and real-world situations [78,79], while also creating realistic occupant DTs using real data [80].

To further assess the realism of the DTs in Co-zyBench, we conducted additional experiments. For the Building DT, we focused on evaluating the realism of its HVAC system simulation, as it is highly dynamic and critical for indoor conditions and energy performance. We compared simulated indoor temperature and HVAC energy consumption against real-world data from the Drahi-X building. This dataset spans two years with records captured every 15 min, covering outdoor conditions, indoor temperatures, and energy consumption for 35 rooms. Since the HVAC system in the building is predominantly set to maintain 25 °C, our analysis focused on periods when the outdoor temperature exceeded 25 °C and the HVAC system was on. The results show that the simulations achieved 98% accuracy for indoor temperatures and an average of 80% accuracy for energy consumption across different outdoor temperature intervals (see Fig. 16). To validate the Occupant DT, we analyzed whether simulated occupant behaviors align with expected behavior patterns. To this end, we modeled an Occupant DT in the Drahi-X building scenario where people, mostly researchers, are expected to spend a significant amount of time in the building, typically engaging in office work, attending meetings, and taking occasional breaks. Based on the analyses, we observe that, on average, occupants spent between 9 to 11 h per day inside the building. Within this timeframe, approximately 7 to 9 h were dedicated to working in their offices, and around 1 h was allocated for lunch breaks. In addition, each occupant attended an average of 3 meetings per week, where the duration of meetings ranged from 10 to 40 min. These findings indicate that the behaviors exhibited by the Occupant DT are consistent with realistic expectations for this scenario.

External Validity. Our benchmark primarily focuses on evaluating thermal comfort provision systems on specific aspects of comfort and energy consumption. The applicability of our benchmark to systems with different concerns, for example, operating lighting and window shading, may be limited. However, such systems can be incorporated into Co-zyBench if simulation tools like EnergyPlus exist and offer an API for integration with the co-simulation middleware.

7. Conclusions

This article presents Co-zyBench, a benchmarking platform for evaluating and optimizing pervasive computing based thermal comfort provision systems in smart buildings in terms of individual thermal comfort, thermal comfort equality, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions and overall performance. In addition, our platform offers flexibility by allowing users to import their Digital Twin model for an accurate assessment of the performance of their systems in specific buildings.

To demonstrate the applicability of Co-zyBench, we conducted experiments by creating Digital Twins of buildings and occupants, analyzing different thermal comfort provision systems to compare their performance in three scenarios ranging from simple models to a real building model. For the scenarios, we assume the observations can facilitate the building administrator to make a decision to employ thermal comfort provision systems based on their requirements. In addition, our analysis reveals that a system performs differently in different building and occupant setups, while it is still possible to develop techniques that can effectively balance equality and thermal comfort while simultaneously reducing energy consumption.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jun Ma: Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Dimitrije Panic:** Writing – review & editing. **Roberto Yus:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Georgios Bouloukakis:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This work is partially supported by the Horizon Europe project PANDORA under grant agreement number 101135775, the China Scholarship Council (CSC 202208070121), and the Energy4Climate Interdisciplinary Center (E4C) of IP Paris, which is in part supported by the 3rd Programme d'Investissements d'Avenir [ANR-18-EUR-0006-02] and by the Foundation of École polytechnique (Chaire “Défis Technologiques pour une Énergie Responsable” financed by TotalEnergies).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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